

Synthesis, characterization and X-ray structure of a mononuclear mercury(II) thiocyanato complex containing a tripodal amine

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Manuscript received online 15 March 2012, revised 05 April 2012, accepted 11 April 2012

Abstract : Mononuclear compound of the type $[\text{Hg}(\text{tren})(\text{SCN})]\text{ClO}_4$ (**1**) [tren = tris(2-aminoethyl)amine] has been isolated and characterized with the help of microanalytical, spectroscopic and single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. Mercury(II) center in **1** adopts a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry with an HgN_4S chromophore. Primary N atoms of tren constitute the basal plane, and remaining tertiary amine N atom and S atom of terminal thiocyanate are in the apical positions. In the crystalline state, complexed cations and counter anions are engaged in N-H...N, N-H...O, N-H...S and C-H...N hydrogen bonds resulting in a 3D network structure.

Keywords : Mercury(II), tris(2-aminoethyl)amine, thiocyanate. X-ray structure.

Introduction

The design and synthesis^{1,2} of coordination compounds of mercury(II) of different nuclearities are continuing unabated because of their outstanding importance in chemistry and materials science with potential applications in paper industry and as thermostat probes, thermoelectric devices, fluorescent lamps, sensors and mercury batteries³. The essential prerequisites for such research are the judicious choice⁴ of organic spacers and inorganic/organic terminals/bridges that may lead to directed properties. Recently, we are interested⁵⁻⁹ in the construction of different coordination molecules through variation of ligand backbones and metal coordination environments; in this regard, tailored polyamine/Schiff base spacers and pseudohalide terminals/bridges have been widely used. The tripodal amine, tris(2-aminoethyl)amine (tren) has bifunctional⁷ property with multiple metal ion binding groups and hydrogen bond donor and acceptor centers affording interesting molecular and crystalline architectures^{7,10}. Thiocyanate^{2,7,8,11} is capable of binding metal centers through its hard N-end and/or soft S-end that leads to different varieties of coordination compounds. The present work stems from our interest to investigate the coordination behaviour of mercury(II) towards tren in concert with thiocyanate, that remains unexplored to date.

Successfully, we have isolated a mononuclear compound of the type $[\text{Hg}(\text{tren})(\text{SCN})]\text{ClO}_4$ (**1**). The details of synthesis, characterization and structure of this complex is described below.

Results and discussion

The pentacoordinated mononuclear compound **1** was obtained in good yield through reaction of a 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$, tren, NH_4NCS and NaClO_4 in MeOH solution at room temperature as shown in eq. (1).

Compound **1** was characterized by elemental analyses, spectroscopic studies and other physicochemical results. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with the formulation **1**. The compound is air-stable and moisture-insensitive, and is soluble in water and in common or-

ganic solvents such as methanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. Solution electrical conductivity measurement¹² in methanol shows that **1** behaves as 1 : 1 electrolyte as evident from their conductivity value ($110 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$). In IR spectra, $\nu(\text{N-H})$ stretching frequencies of the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups of tren are found at 3347 and 3272 cm^{-1} , along with weak band at 2916 cm^{-1} assignable to aliphatic C-H stretching vibration. $\nu(\text{CN})$ stretches of the thiocyanate ligand appear at 2108 , 2049 and 2031 cm^{-1} ; the band at $>2100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates S-coordination¹¹. Band corresponding to $\nu(\text{C-S})$ stretching frequency of terminal S-coordination is observed at 745 cm^{-1} . The presence of perchlorate stretches at 1145 , 1112 , 1081 and 626 cm^{-1} is indicative of non-coordination¹³ to the metal centers. Colourless MeOH solution of **1** shows bands at 225 and 268 nm assignable to ligand based transition¹⁴.

In order to define the coordination sphere conclusively, single-crystal X-ray diffraction study of **1** was made. An ORTEP diagram with atom numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 1. Selected interatomic bond lengths and bond angles are listed in Table 1. Significant hydrogen bond-

ing data are set in Table 2. Structural analysis reveals that asymmetric unit in **1** contains four mononuclear $[\text{Hg}(\text{tren})(\text{SCN})]\text{ClO}_4$ moieties (A, B, C and D). Each mercury(II) center (Hg1 for A, Hg2 for B, Hg3 for C and Hg4 for D) has a distorted trigonal bipyramidal [$\tau = 0.95$ (Hg1), 0.87 (Hg2), 0.93 (Hg3) and 0.83 (Hg4)] environment with an HgN_4S chromophore (Fig. 1) coordinated by four amine N atoms of tren and one S atom of terminal thiocyanate. Three primary amine N (N3, N15, N17/N1, N2, N10/N4, N5, N13/N12, N16, N19 for Hg1/Hg2/Hg3/Hg4) atoms of the tripodal amine define the equatorial plane and the remaining tertiary amine N (N14/N9/N6/N7 for Hg1/Hg2/Hg3/Hg4) atom of tren and the S (S9/S1/S13/S4 for Hg1/Hg2/Hg3/Hg4) atom of thiocyanate occupy the axial positions. Bite angles of the three five membered chelate loops lie in the range $72.5(5)$ – $75.7(5)^\circ$. Equatorial/axial bond angles are close to the ideal value ($120^\circ/180^\circ$) except the axial angle S4-Hg4-N7 in molecule D reflecting substantial deviation [$163.6(3)^\circ$]. Hg-N(tren) bond distances in the equatorial plane lie in the range $2.307(14)$ – $2.328(14) \text{ \AA}$ (for A), $2.267(13)$ – $2.364(15) \text{ \AA}$ (for B), $2.293(14)$ – $2.334(12) \text{ \AA}$

Fig. 1. A view of the title compound **1** with atom-labelling scheme. Displacement ellipsoids are drawn at the 20% probability level. H atoms are omitted for clarity.

Table 1. Selected interatomic distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1**

Bond distances :			
Hg1-N17	2.307(14)	Hg2-N2	2.267(13)
Hg1-N15	2.310(13)	Hg2-N10	2.350(12)
Hg1-N3	2.328(14)	Hg2-N1	2.364(15)
Hg1-S9	2.527(5)	Hg2-S1	2.518(4)
Hg1-N14	2.536(12)	Hg2-N9	2.535(11)
Hg3-N13	2.293(14)	Hg4-N12	2.266(14)
Hg3-N4	2.327(14)	Hg4-N16	2.348(13)
Hg3-N5	2.334(12)	Hg4-N19	2.403(17)
Hg3-S13	2.533(5)	Hg4-S4	2.495(4)
Hg3-N6	2.540(12)	Hg4-N7	2.519(13)
S1-C13	1.666(19)	C13-N11	1.11(2)
S9-C26	1.71(2)	C26-N20	1.14(2)
S4-C27	1.62(2)	C27-N21	1.18(3)
S13-C22	1.71(2)	C22-N18	1.10(2)
Bond angles :			
N17-Hg1-N15	116.9(6)	N2-Hg2-N10	110.1(5)
N17-Hg1-N3	111.3(6)	N2-Hg2-N1	117.8(6)
N15-Hg1-N3	110.5(5)	N10-Hg2-N1	110.4(5)
S9-Hg1-N14	174.5(3)	S1-Hg2-N9	170.1(3)
N15-Hg1-N14	74.4(4)	N2-Hg2-N9	74.1(4)
N17-Hg1-N14	73.9(5)	N10-Hg2-N9	74.6(4)
N3-Hg1-N14	74.4(4)	N1-Hg2-N9	73.6(4)
N13-Hg3-N4	117.4(6)	N12-Hg4-N16	111.8(5)
N4-Hg3-N5	110.0(5)	N12-Hg4-N19	114.1(5)
N13-Hg3-N5	110.5(5)	N16-Hg4-N19	111.9(6)
S13-Hg3-N6	173.1(3)	S4-Hg4-N7	163.6(3)
N13-Hg3-N6	73.8(5)	N12-Hg4-N7	75.7(5)
N4-Hg3-N6	73.8(4)	N16-Hg4-N7	73.4(4)
N5-Hg3-N6	74.2(4)	N19-Hg4-N7	72.5(5)
N18-C22-S13	179(2)	N20-C26-S9	178.8(19)
N11-C13-S1	177.1(19)	N21-C27-S4	169.2(19)

(for C) and 2.266(14)–2.403(17) Å (for D) which are somewhat shorter compared to axial Hg-S(NCS) (Table 1) bond lengths. Each mercury(II) center deviates considerably [0.628 Å (Hg1), 0.638 Å (Hg2), 0.642 Å (Hg3) and 0.649 Å (Hg4)] from the mean equatorial plane containing three primary amine N atom of tren. In A-D, the linear terminal thiocyanate unit are coordinated to the mercury(II) centers in a bending fashion as reflected in their bond angle values [C26-S9-Hg1 95.6(6)°, C13-S1-Hg2 95.6(6)°, C22-S13-Hg3 96.7(6)° and C27-S4-Hg4 102.3(6)°]. Here, it is worth-mentioning that the reported mercury(II) thiocyanate analog⁸ using a tetradentate Schiff base, *N,N'*-(bis-(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,2-ethanedi-

Table 2. Hydrogen bond parameters (Å, °)

D-H-A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
N1-H1A...N11 ^a	0.90	2.42	3.21(2)	147
N1-H1B...O8 ^b	0.90	2.56	3.29(2)	138
N2-H2A...N21 ^c	0.90	2.41	3.13(3)	137
N2-H2B...O21 ^d	0.90	2.20	3.09(3)	166
N3-H3A...O10 ^e	0.90	2.19	3.07(2)	165
N3-H3B...O1	0.90	2.24	3.08(2)	156
N4-H4B...N20 ^f	0.90	2.31	3.12(2)	150
N5-H5A...O22	0.90	2.59	3.26(5)	132
N5-H5A...O25	0.90	2.33	3.19(5)	160
N5-H5B...O9	0.90	2.13	3.02(2)	169
N10-H10C...O6 ^b	0.90	2.27	3.100(19)	153
N12-H12C...O14 ^g	0.90	2.39	3.22(3)	155
N12-H12C...O22 ^g	0.90	2.44	3.22(5)	145
N12-H12D...O12 ^h	0.90	2.53	3.22(3)	135
N13-H13A...O2 ^f	0.90	2.14	3.02(2)	166
N15-H15B...O25	0.90	2.23	3.01(5)	145
N16-H16C...O11 ^h	0.90	2.26	3.15(3)	170
N16-H16D...S13	0.90	2.68	3.553(14)	163
N17-H17C...N18	0.90	2.29	3.14(3)	156
N19-H19A...O3 ^f	0.90	2.30	3.16(2)	158
C11-H11A...N21 ^c	0.97	2.42	3.18(3)	134

Symmetry code : (a) $x, 2-y, -1/2+z$; (b) $1+x, 2-y, 1/2+z$; (c) $x, y, 1+z$; (d) $x, 1+y, z$; (e) $x, 2-y, 1/2+z$; (f) $x, y, -1+z$; (g) $1/2+x, 3/2-y, -1/2+z$; (h) $x, 1-y, -1/2+z$.

amine, as organic blocker is a neutral dinuclear entity where each metal center is tetracoordinated through bis(bidentate) congregation behaviour of the Schiff base and S-coordinated terminal pseudohalides. So, an interesting change in the nuclearity from neutral dinuclear to monocationic mononuclear compound is revealed through a change from Schiff base to tripodal amine with same denticity.

In crystalline state, among four different mononuclear units in **1**, molecules A and C are engaged in single N-H...N (N4-H4B...N20 and N17-H17C...N18) hydrogen bonds resulting in a 1D chain; whereas B and D are associated affording an another distinct 1D zig-zag chain in the same direction through single N-H...N (N1-H1A...N11) and bifurcated N-H...N and C-H...N (N2-H2A...N21 and C11-H11A...N21) hydrogen bonds (Table 2). These two distinctly different 1D chains are connected to each other through N-H...S hydrogen bonds (N16-H16D...S13) involving coordinated S atom of thiocyanate (in C) and H atoms of -NH₂ groups of tren (in D)

affording a 3D network structure (Fig. 2). The counter anions embedded in between the void spaces of the 3D network are engaged in multiple N-H...O (Table 2) hydrogen bonds and strengthen the solid state structure.

Caution! Mercury and its compounds are toxic¹⁵. Perchlorate compounds of metal ions are potentially explosive¹⁶ especially in the presence of organic ligands. Only a small amount of these materials should be prepared and

Fig. 2. Perspective view of 3D network structure in **1** formed by multiple cooperative N-H...N, N-H...S, C-H...N and N-H...O hydrogen bonds involving complex cations and perchlorate counter anions.

In conclusion, one mononuclear mercury(II) thiocyanate complex in combination with a tripodal amine is isolated and characterized. Structure of **1** is solved by X-ray diffraction measurement to establish the coordination sphere in which terminal pseudohalide and counter anion act as proton acceptors and metalated -NH₂/-CH₂ groups of tren as proton donors towards building up of a 3D supramolecular architecture.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity tris(2-aminoethyl)amine (Fluka, Germany), ammonium thiocyanate (E. Merck, India), mercury(II) acetate (E. Merck, India) and sodium perchlorate (Lancaster, UK) were purchased from respective concerns. All other chemicals and solvents were AR grade and used as received.

handled with care.

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were done using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectrum (KBr disc, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) was recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Ground state absorption measurement (in MeOH) was made with a Shimadzu model UV-2450 UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Preparation of complex :

[Hg(tren)(SCN)]ClO₄ (**1**) : Hg(OAc)₂ (318 mg, 1 mmol) and tren (146 mg, 1 mmol) each in 10 ml methanol were taken in separate containers and mixed together slowly. To this colourless mixture, a methanolic solution (5 ml) of NH₄NCS (76 mg, 1 mmol) followed by NaClO₄ (140 mg, 1 mmol) dissolved in the same solvent (5 ml) was added dropwise. The final colourless solution was filtered and left undisturbed in an open air for slow evapo-

ration. Within a week colourless rectangular crystals of **1** that separated, were collected by filtration and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 363 mg (72%). Found : C, 16.70; H, 3.57; N, 13.97. Calcd. for $C_7H_{18}N_5O_4SClHg$ (**1**) : C, 16.66; H, 3.59; N, 13.94%. IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(N-H)$ 3347, 3272; $\nu(C-H)$ 2916; $\nu(NCS)$ 2108, 2049, 2031; $\nu(C-S)$ 745; $\nu(ClO_4)$ 1145, 1112, 1081, 626. UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm in MeOH) : 225, 268.

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

X-Ray diffraction data of **1** were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX-11 CCD area-detector diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 150 K with the Oxford Cryosystem Cobra low-temperature attachment. The unit cell parameters were obtained from SAINT¹⁷ absorption corrections were performed with SADABS¹⁸. The structures were solved by direct methods, and refined by full matrix least-squares method based on $|F|^2$ using SHELXL-97¹⁹. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters whereas hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions and given isotropic *U* values 1.2 times that of the atom to which they are bound. All calculations were carried out using PLATON²⁰ and ORTEP-32²¹. A summary of the crystallographic data and structure determination parameters is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Crystallographic data for $[Hg(tren)(SCN)]ClO_4$ (**1**)

Crystallographic parameter	1
Chemical formula	$C_7H_{18}N_5O_4SClHg$
Formula mass	504.36
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	Cc
Crystal size (mm^3)	$0.21 \times 0.17 \times 0.14$
<i>D</i> (cal) ($g\ cm^{-3}$)	2.242
<i>a</i> (\AA)	16.886(3)
<i>b</i> (\AA)	28.001(5)
<i>c</i> (\AA)	12.644(2)
α ($^\circ$)	90.00
β ($^\circ$)	91.585(2)
γ ($^\circ$)	90.00
Unit cell volume (\AA^3)	5975.9(18)
Temperature (K)	150(2)

Table-3 (contd.)

<i>F</i> (000)	3840
No. of formula units per unit cell (<i>Z</i>)	16
Absorption coefficient (μ/mm^{-1})	10.637
θ range for data collection ($^\circ$)	1.41 to 25.00
<i>h/k/l</i>	-20, 20/-33, 33/-15, 14
<i>T</i> _{min} and <i>T</i> _{max}	0.13 and 0.23
No. of reflections measured	28135
No. of independent reflections	10094
Data/restraints/parameters	10094/32/685
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.0767
Final <i>R</i> ₁ values (<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>))	0.0522
Final <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²) values (<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>))	0.1130
Final <i>R</i> ₁ values (all data)	0.0651
Final <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²) values (all data)	0.1194
Goodness of fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.000
Largest peak and hole ($e\text{\AA}^{-3}$)	2.196 and -1.829
$R = \Sigma F_o - F_c / \Sigma F_o $, $wR = [\Sigma w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \Sigma w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, calcd. $w = 1/\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0465P)^2 + 0.0000P$; where $P = (F_o^2 - 2F_c^2)/3$.	

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data (excluding structure factors) for **1** has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre No. CCDC 784616. Copies of this information can be obtained, free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

Acknowledgement

Financial support from DST and CSIR, New Delhi, India is gratefully acknowledged. KB and SK are grateful to CSIR and SC, to UGC, New Delhi, India for fellowships. The authors acknowledge the use of DST-funded National Single Crystal X-Ray Diffraction Facility at the Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata, India for crystallographic studies.

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